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Beyond a solvent: Triple roles of dimethylformamide in organic chemistry

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Abstract

N,N-Dimethylformamide (DMF) is frequently used as an aprotic solvent in chemical transformations in laboratories of academia as well as in those of chemical industry. In the present review, we will reveal that DMF is actually something much more than a solvent. It is a unique chemical since, as well as being an effective polar aprotic solvent, it can play three other important roles in organic chemistry. It can be used as a reagent, a catalyst, and a stabilizer.

Keyword: Chemical industry, Dimethylformamide, Aprotic solvents, Chemical transformations, N,N Dimethylformamide, Organic Chemistry, Polar aprotic solvent, Organic solvents